

A Verifiable Secret Sharing Protocol Based on Isogenies for Post-Quantum Cryptography

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Abstract—We propose a novel Verifiable Secret Sharing (VSS) protocol utilizing isogenies of supersingular elliptic curves to ensure robust security in a post-quantum environment. By exploiting the computational hardness of the Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP), our protocol achieves resistance against quantum attacks. We integrate Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP) to enable participants to verify share validity without compromising the secret. Through rigorous mathematical proofs and performance analysis, we demonstrate that our protocol not only enhances security but also maintains computational efficiency compared to existing schemes, making it highly suitable for applications requiring long-term security such as blockchain technologies and secure multi-party computations.

Index Terms—Isogeny-based cryptography, Verifiable Secret Sharing (VSS), Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP), Post-Quantum Cryptography, Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP), Elliptic Curve Cryptography.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of quantum computing technology poses a significant threat to classical cryptographic systems. Quantum algorithms, such as Shor's algorithm [?], can efficiently solve the integer factorization and discrete logarithm problems, rendering many widely used cryptosystems insecure. This imminent threat has spurred extensive research into post-quantum cryptography, which aims to develop cryptographic protocols secure against quantum adversaries [?].

Among the various approaches to post-quantum cryptography, isogeny-based cryptography has emerged as a promising candidate due to its strong security assumptions and relatively small key sizes compared to other post-quantum schemes [18]. Isogeny-based cryptographic protocols rely on the hardness of finding isogenies between supersingular elliptic curves, a problem believed to be intractable even for quantum computers [17]. Notably, the Supersingular Isogeny Diffie-Hellman (SIDH) protocol has been proposed as a quantum-resistant alternative to classical Diffie-Hellman key exchange [17].

Verifiable Secret Sharing (VSS) protocols are fundamental components in secure multiparty computations and distributed systems. They enable a dealer to distribute a secret among a group of participants such that only authorized subsets can reconstruct the secret, and participants can verify the integrity of their shares [15]. VSS protocols ensure that even

if some participants are dishonest, the honest parties can still reconstruct the correct secret without being misled by invalid shares.

However, existing VSS schemes, such as Shamir's Secret Sharing [15] and Pedersen's VSS [16], are vulnerable in the context of quantum computing. These schemes rely on mathematical problems that can be efficiently solved by quantum algorithms, compromising their security. Consequently, there is a pressing need to develop VSS protocols that are secure against quantum adversaries.

Several post-quantum VSS schemes have been proposed, utilizing hard problems from code-based [20] and lattice-based cryptography [19]. While these schemes offer security against quantum attacks, they often suffer from high computational and communication overheads, making them less practical for real-world applications. Moreover, they may involve large key sizes and complex operations, which can hinder their adoption.

Contributions: In this paper, we propose a novel Verifiable Secret Sharing protocol based on isogenies of supersingular elliptic curves, aiming to provide robust security in a post-quantum context while maintaining computational and communication efficiency. Our main contributions are as follows:

- 1) We introduce a VSS protocol that leverages the hardness of the Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP), ensuring security against quantum adversaries. By encoding the secret as the j -invariant of a supersingular elliptic curve and using isogenies for share generation, we provide a secure foundation for the protocol.
- 2) We integrate Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP) based on isogenies to enable participants to verify the validity of their shares without revealing any sensitive information. The ZKPs ensure that a dishonest dealer cannot distribute invalid shares undetected, preserving the integrity of the secret sharing process.
- 3) We provide rigorous mathematical proofs demonstrating the security and correctness of the protocol. Our analysis includes proofs of confidentiality, soundness, zero-knowledge properties, and post-quantum security, highlighting the protocol's robustness against various adversarial behaviors.
- 4) We conduct a detailed efficiency analysis, examining the computational and communication complexities of the

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protocol. We compare our scheme with existing VSS protocols, demonstrating that it achieves a favorable balance between security and efficiency, making it suitable for practical applications.

Related Work: Several attempts have been made to develop VSS protocols secure against quantum adversaries. Code-based VSS schemes, such as those based on the McEliece cryptosystem [20], offer post-quantum security but often require large key sizes and have significant computational overhead. Lattice-based VSS protocols leverage the hardness of lattice problems like the Learning With Errors (LWE) problem [19], providing quantum-resistant security but also facing challenges in efficiency and implementation complexity.

Isogeny-based cryptography, while relatively new, has been explored for constructing various cryptographic primitives. De Feo et al. [6] proposed an isogeny-based identification scheme, and subsequent work has extended isogeny-based methods to other cryptographic applications. However, to the best of our knowledge, there has been no prior work on developing a Verifiable Secret Sharing protocol based on isogenies of supersingular elliptic curves. Our work fills this gap by introducing a VSS protocol that combines isogeny-based cryptography with Zero-Knowledge Proofs to achieve post-quantum security with practical efficiency.

Organization of the Paper: The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we provide the necessary mathematical preliminaries, including an overview of elliptic curves, isogenies, supersingular elliptic curves, and Zero-Knowledge Proofs. Section III describes the proposed VSS protocol in detail, including the protocol steps and cryptographic components. In Section IV, we present a comprehensive security analysis, providing proofs of the protocol's security properties. Section V offers an efficiency analysis, examining the computational and communication complexities and discussing optimization strategies. In Section VI, we compare our protocol with existing VSS schemes, highlighting the advantages of our approach. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper and suggests directions for future research.

II. MATHEMATICAL PRELIMINARIES

A. Elliptic Curves and Isogenies

An elliptic curve E over a finite field $\mathbb{F}_q$ is given by a simplified Weierstrass equation:

$$E : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b,$$

where $a, b \in \mathbb{F}_q$, and the discriminant $\Delta = -16(4a^3 + 27b^2) \neq 0$ ensures that the curve is non-singular [4].

The set of points $E(\mathbb{F}_q)$, including the point at infinity O , forms a finite abelian group under the point addition operation.

Definition II.1 (Isogeny). An isogeny is a morphism of elliptic curves $\phi : E \rightarrow E'$ that is a group homomorphism, i.e.,

$$\forall P, Q \in E, \quad \phi(P + Q) = \phi(P) + \phi(Q).$$

Isogenies are non-constant rational maps of finite degree. The degree of an isogeny ϕ is defined as the degree of the rational map, which is equal to the size of its kernel $\ker(\phi)$.

Theorem II.1 (Properties of Isogenies). Let E, E' be elliptic curves and $\phi : E \rightarrow E'$ an isogeny of degree m . Then:

- 1) The kernel $\ker(\phi)$ is a subgroup of E of order m .
- 2) There exists a dual isogeny $\hat{\phi} : E' \rightarrow E$ such that $\hat{\phi} \circ \phi = [m]$, where $[m]$ is the multiplication-by- m map on E .

Proof. See [4], Chapter III, for a detailed proof of these fundamental properties of isogenies. $\square$

B. Supersingular Elliptic Curves

An elliptic curve is *supersingular* if its number of points over $\mathbb{F}_q$ is congruent to 1 modulo p , where p is the characteristic of the field $\mathbb{F}_q$. These curves have special properties that make them useful for isogeny-based cryptography.

Theorem II.2 (Properties of Supersingular Curves). Supersingular elliptic curves over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$ have an endomorphism ring isomorphic to a maximal order in a quaternion algebra over $\mathbb{Q}$.

Proof. Refer to [5] for a detailed proof connecting the endomorphisms of supersingular curves to quaternion algebras. $\square$

C. Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP)

The SIP is considered a hard problem, even for quantum computers, making it a solid foundation for post-quantum cryptography.

Definition II.2 (Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP)). Given two supersingular elliptic curves E and E' defined over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$, find an isogeny $\phi : E \rightarrow E'$.

Theorem II.3 (Hardness of the SIP). The SIP is a hard problem with exponential complexity in $\log p$, even for quantum computers. No sub-exponential algorithm is known to solve it.

Proof. The hardness of the SIP is linked to the structure of the supersingular isogeny graph, which is a Ramanujan graph with strong expansion properties [2], [18]. Navigating this graph to find a specific isogeny is equivalent to an unstructured search in an exponential space, for which quantum algorithms like Grover's algorithm only offer a quadratic speedup, insufficient to reduce the complexity to a practical level. $\square$

D. Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP)

ZKPs allow one party to prove knowledge of a secret without revealing it, which is essential for verifiability in our protocol.

Definition II.3 (Zero-Knowledge Property). A proof system is zero-knowledge if, for any probabilistic polynomial-time verifier V^* , there exists a simulator S capable of producing a transcript indistinguishable from one resulting from an actual interaction between the honest prover and V^* , without knowledge of the secret.

1) *Properties of ZKPs*: ZKPs must satisfy three properties:

- 1) **Completeness**: If the statement is true and both parties follow the protocol, the verifier will accept the proof.
- 2) **Soundness**: If the statement is false, no cheating prover can convince the verifier that it is true, except with negligible probability.
- 3) **Zero-Knowledge**: The verifier learns nothing other than the truth of the statement.

2) *ZKP for Isogenies*: We use an interactive protocol based on isogenies to prove knowledge of a secret isogeny $\phi : E \rightarrow E'$ without revealing it.

Theorem II.4. *There exists a zero-knowledge proof protocol to prove knowledge of an isogeny between two supersingular curves.*

Proof. The protocol proceeds as follows:

- 1) **Commitment**: The prover selects a random isogeny $\psi : E \rightarrow E''$ and sends E'' to the verifier.
- 2) **Challenge**: The verifier sends a random bit $c \in \{0, 1\}$.
- 3) **Response**:
 - If $c = 0$, the prover sends ψ .
 - If $c = 1$, the prover sends $\phi \circ \psi$.
- 4) **Verification**:
 - If $c = 0$, the verifier checks that ψ is a valid isogeny from E to E'' .
 - If $c = 1$, the verifier checks that $\phi \circ \psi$ is a valid isogeny from E to E' .

This protocol satisfies completeness, soundness, and zero-knowledge properties, as detailed in [6]. □

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROTOCOL

A. Overview

The proposed Verifiable Secret Sharing (VSS) protocol aims to securely distribute a secret s among n participants in such a way that any subset of at least t participants can reconstruct the secret, while fewer than t participants cannot gain any information about it. The secret s is encoded using the j -invariant of a supersingular elliptic curve E , denoted as $s = j(E)$. The protocol leverages the hardness of the Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP) for security and integrates Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP) to ensure verifiability without revealing sensitive information.

B. Protocol Steps

The protocol consists of the following detailed steps:

1) Initialization

- a) The *dealer* selects a supersingular elliptic curve E defined over the finite field $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$, ensuring that the j -invariant $s = j(E)$ represents the secret to be shared.
- b) Security parameters are chosen, including the prime p , the threshold t , and the degrees of the isogenies to be used.

2) Share Generation

- a) The dealer constructs a random polynomial $P(x)$ of degree $t - 1$ over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$:

$$P(x) = s + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_{t-1}x^{t-1},$$

where a_i are random coefficients in $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$.

- b) Each participant P_i is assigned a unique public identifier $x_i \in \mathbb{F}_{p^2}$, with $x_i \neq x_j$ for $i \neq j$.
- c) The dealer computes the share $s_i = P(x_i)$ for each participant P_i .

3) Isogeny Generation

- a) For each share s_i , the dealer generates a secret isogeny $\phi_i : E \rightarrow E_i$ such that the j -invariant of E_i satisfies $j(E_i) = s_i$.
- b) The isogeny ϕ_i is constructed by selecting a random kernel subgroup $\ker(\phi_i) \subset E$ of order corresponding to the degree ℓ , a small prime or prime power chosen for efficiency and security.
- c) The curves E_i and the isogenies ϕ_i are kept secret by the dealer to prevent any leakage of information about the secret s .

4) Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) Generation

- a) For each participant P_i , the dealer prepares a ZKP to convince P_i that the share s_i is valid, i.e., that it corresponds to a valid isogeny from E to E_i without revealing ϕ_i or s .
- b) The ZKP is based on an interactive protocol (e.g., a Sigma protocol) that demonstrates knowledge of ϕ_i without disclosing it.

5) Distribution of Shares

- a) The dealer securely sends to each participant P_i the tuple (s_i, ZKP_i) , where s_i is the share and ZKP_i is the Zero-Knowledge Proof corresponding to s_i .
- b) The communication channel should be secure and authenticated to prevent interception or tampering by adversaries.

6) Verification of Shares

- a) Upon receiving (s_i, ZKP_i) , each participant P_i performs the ZKP verification procedure to confirm that s_i is a valid share derived from E .
- b) If the verification succeeds, P_i accepts the share; otherwise, P_i rejects it and notifies the dealer (and possibly other participants) of the invalid share.

7) Secret Reconstruction

- a) When a group of at least t participants $\{P_{i_1}, P_{i_2}, \dots, P_{i_t}\}$ decide to reconstruct the secret, they share their verified shares s_{i_k} among themselves.
- b) Using Lagrange interpolation over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$, they reconstruct the polynomial $P(x)$:

$$P(x) = \sum_{k=1}^t s_{i_k} \cdot \lambda_{i_k}(x),$$

where $\lambda_{i_k}(x)$ are the Lagrange basis polynomials defined as:

$$\lambda_{i_k}(x) = \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq k}}^t \frac{x - x_{i_j}}{x_{i_k} - x_{i_j}}.$$

c) The secret s is then recovered by evaluating $P(0)$:

$$s = P(0) = \sum_{k=1}^t s_{i_k} \cdot \lambda_{i_k}(0).$$

C. Cryptographic Details

In this subsection, we delve deeper into the cryptographic components of the protocol.

1) Secret Encoding:

- The secret s is mapped to the j -invariant of a supersingular elliptic curve E .
- The j -invariant uniquely identifies the isomorphism class of E over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$.
- Choosing $s = j(E)$ ensures that the secret is compatible with the isogeny operations used in the protocol.

2) Polynomial Construction:

- The dealer selects random coefficients $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{t-1}$ from $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$ to construct the polynomial $P(x)$ of degree $t-1$.
- The constant term of $P(x)$ is set to the secret s , ensuring that $P(0) = s$.
- This polynomial serves as the sharing polynomial in Shamir's Secret Sharing scheme, adapted to work over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$.

3) Isogeny Generation:

- For each participant P_i , the dealer needs to find an elliptic curve E_i such that $j(E_i) = s_i$.
- The dealer constructs an isogeny $\phi_i : E \rightarrow E_i$ by selecting a random kernel subgroup $\ker(\phi_i) \subset E$ of order ℓ , where ℓ is a small prime or prime power.
- The isogeny ϕ_i is computed using Vélu's formulas [13], which provide explicit equations for the isogeny based on its kernel.
- The secrecy of ϕ_i is crucial, as revealing it could compromise the security of the secret s .

4) *Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) Generation:* The dealer must convince each participant P_i that s_i is correctly derived without revealing ϕ_i or E . The ZKP protocol proceeds as follows [6]:

1) Commitment Phase:

- a) The dealer selects a random isogeny $\psi_i : E \rightarrow E'_i$ of degree ℓ and computes $E'_i = \psi_i(E)$.
- b) The dealer sends E'_i to P_i as a commitment.

2) Challenge Phase:

- a) P_i selects a random challenge bit $c \in \{0, 1\}$ and sends it to the dealer.

3) Response Phase:

- a) If $c = 0$:

- i) The dealer sends ψ_i to P_i .
- b) If $c = 1$:
 - i) The dealer computes the composed isogeny $\varphi_i = \phi_i \circ \psi_i$ and sends φ_i to P_i .

4) Verification Phase:

- a) If $c = 0$:
 - i) P_i verifies that ψ_i is a valid isogeny from E to E'_i of degree ℓ .
- b) If $c = 1$:
 - i) P_i verifies that φ_i is a valid isogeny from E to E_i .

This protocol is repeated k times to reduce the soundness error to 2^{-k} , ensuring a high level of confidence in the validity of the share.

5) Secret Reconstruction:

- Participants use Lagrange interpolation to reconstruct the polynomial $P(x)$ given t valid shares.
- All computations are performed in $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$ to maintain consistency with the encoding of the secret.
- The security of the reconstruction process relies on the integrity of the shares and the correctness of the interpolation.

IV. SECURITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the security properties of the proposed protocol, demonstrating its robustness against various adversarial behaviors.

A. Confidentiality

Theorem IV.1 (Confidentiality). *No coalition of fewer than t participants can reconstruct or gain any information about the secret s .*

Proof. The confidentiality of the secret relies on the polynomial $P(x)$ used in Shamir's Secret Sharing scheme [15], which has the property that any $t-1$ or fewer shares provide no information about $P(0) = s$.

Specifically, the set of shares $\{s_{i_1}, s_{i_2}, \dots, s_{i_{t-1}}\}$ corresponds to $t-1$ equations in t unknowns (the coefficients of $P(x)$). There are infinitely many polynomials of degree $t-1$ that fit these shares, resulting in a uniform distribution of possible secrets from the perspective of the adversary.

Furthermore, without knowledge of the isogenies ϕ_i , participants cannot relate their shares s_i back to the original curve E or the secret $s = j(E)$, due to the hardness of the Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP). Solving the SIP to find an isogeny between E_i and an unknown E is computationally infeasible, even with quantum capabilities [17], [18].

Thus, the protocol ensures that any coalition of fewer than t participants cannot reconstruct s or glean any information about it. $\square$

B. Soundness and Authenticity

Theorem IV.2 (Soundness). *A dishonest dealer cannot convince honest participants to accept invalid shares without being detected during the verification process.*

Proof. The soundness of the protocol is guaranteed by the Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs) used during the share verification phase. The ZKPs are designed to be sound, meaning that if the dealer attempts to cheat by providing an invalid share s_i (i.e., one not derived from the polynomial $P(x)$ or the curve E), the probability that the participant P_i accepts the share is negligible.

In the ZKP protocol, the dealer must respond correctly to the participant's challenge $c \in \{0, 1\}$:

- If the dealer tries to cheat, they cannot produce valid responses for both cases of c without knowledge of a valid isogeny ϕ_i corresponding to s_i .
- The protocol's soundness error is $\epsilon = 1/2^k$, where k is the number of iterations. By choosing a sufficiently large k , the dealer's chance of successfully cheating becomes negligible.

Therefore, the protocol ensures that any invalid shares will be detected by honest participants during the verification phase. $\square$

C. Zero-Knowledge Property

Theorem IV.3 (Zero-Knowledge). *The ZKP protocol does not reveal any information about the secret s , the isogenies ϕ_i , or the curve E to the participants.*

Proof. The Zero-Knowledge Proofs are constructed to satisfy the zero-knowledge property, which implies that the verifier (participant P_i) learns nothing beyond the validity of the statement being proven.

This is achieved by:

- The dealer's responses are either ψ_i or $\varphi_i = \phi_i \circ \psi_i$, both of which do not reveal ϕ_i or E individually.
- For each challenge, the dealer uses fresh randomness, preventing the participant from gaining information by combining multiple transcripts.
- There exists a simulator that can generate indistinguishable transcripts without knowledge of ϕ_i or s , ensuring that the participant cannot extract any additional information [6].

Therefore, the protocol maintains the secrecy of the underlying cryptographic elements while allowing participants to verify their shares. $\square$

D. Post-Quantum Security

Theorem IV.4 (Post-Quantum Security). *The protocol remains secure against adversaries equipped with quantum computing capabilities, under the assumption that the Supersingular Isogeny Problem (SIP) is hard for quantum computers.*

Proof. The security of the protocol against quantum adversaries relies on two main factors:

- 1) **Hardness of the SIP:** The SIP is believed to be resistant to quantum attacks, as there are no known quantum algorithms capable of solving it in sub-exponential time. Quantum algorithms like Shor's algorithm are effective against problems like integer factorization and discrete logarithms but do not apply to the SIP [?], [17], [18].
- 2) **Security of the ZKP:** The Zero-Knowledge Proofs used in the protocol are constructed without relying on assumptions that are vulnerable to quantum algorithms. The soundness and zero-knowledge properties hold in the presence of quantum adversaries.

Thus, even if an adversary has access to a quantum computer, they cannot:

- Solve the SIP to derive E from E_i and s_i .
- Break the soundness or zero-knowledge properties of the ZKP to obtain ϕ_i or s .

Therefore, the protocol provides post-quantum security, maintaining its robustness in the face of quantum computational threats. $\square$

V. EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS

In this section, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the computational and communication efficiency of the proposed Verifiable Secret Sharing (VSS) protocol. We examine the computational complexity for both the dealer and participants, analyze the communication overhead, and discuss optimization strategies to enhance performance. Comparisons with existing protocols are also provided to contextualize the efficiency of our scheme.

A. Computational Complexity

1) *Dealer's Computation:* The dealer performs several computational tasks during the execution of the protocol. The complexity of these tasks is analyzed as follows:

1) Polynomial Construction:

- Generating a random polynomial $P(x)$ of degree $t - 1$ involves selecting $t - 1$ random coefficients from $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$.
- The time complexity for this step is $O(t)$, where t is the threshold.

2) Share Computation:

- Computing the shares $s_i = P(x_i)$ for all n participants requires evaluating the polynomial $P(x)$ at n distinct points x_i .
- Each evaluation of $P(x_i)$ requires $O(t)$ field operations (multiplications and additions in $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$).
- The total time complexity is $O(nt)$.

3) Isogeny Generation:

- For each participant P_i , the dealer generates an isogeny $\phi_i : E \rightarrow E_i$ of degree ℓ .
- Computing an isogeny of degree ℓ using Vélu's formulas [13] requires $O(\ell)$ group operations on E .
- Assuming ℓ is a small constant (e.g., a small prime), the time complexity per isogeny is $O(1)$.

- The total time complexity for isogeny generation is $O(n)$.

4) Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) Generation:

- For each participant, the dealer engages in k iterations of the ZKP protocol to reduce the soundness error to 2^{-k} .
- Each iteration involves generating a random isogeny ψ_i and computing a composed isogeny $\varphi_i = \phi_i \circ \psi_i$.
- The time complexity per iteration per participant is $O(1)$, assuming small-degree isogenies.
- The total time complexity for ZKP generation is $O(nk)$.

5) Total Dealer Computation:

- Summing up the complexities:

$$O(t) + O(nt) + O(n) + O(nk) = O(nt) + O(nk)$$

- Since t and k are parameters much smaller than n in practical scenarios, the overall complexity is $O(nt)$.

2) *Participant's Computation:* Each participant P_i performs the following computations:

1) Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZKP) Verification:

- The participant engages in k iterations of the ZKP protocol.
- Each iteration involves verifying an isogeny of degree ℓ .
- The time complexity per iteration is $O(1)$, assuming small-degree isogenies.
- The total time complexity for ZKP verification is $O(k)$.

2) Secret Reconstruction (when participating):

- During the reconstruction phase, participants compute Lagrange interpolation coefficients.
- Computing the Lagrange basis polynomials requires $O(t^2)$ field operations.
- Evaluating $P(0)$ using the shares involves $O(t)$ multiplications.
- The total time complexity for secret reconstruction is $O(t^2)$.

3) Total Participant Computation:

- The overall time complexity is $O(k) + O(t^2)$.
- Since k and t are relatively small, the computation is efficient for participants.

B. Communication Complexity

Communication overhead is analyzed based on the data transmitted between the dealer and participants.

1) *Dealer to Participant Communication:* For each participant P_i :

- **Share Transmission:**

- The dealer sends the share $s_i \in \mathbb{F}_{p^2}$, which requires transmitting $2 \log_2 p$ bits.

- **Zero-Knowledge Proof Data:**

- In each of the k iterations, the dealer sends:

- * The curve E'_i in the commitment phase.

- * The isogeny ψ_i or φ_i in the response phase.

- Representing an elliptic curve over $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$ requires transmitting its coefficients, amounting to $O(\log_2 p)$ bits.

- The isogenies can be represented by their kernel generators, which also require $O(\log_2 p)$ bits.

- The total communication per participant is $O(k \log_2 p)$ bits.

- **Total Dealer to Participant Communication:**

- The total communication per participant is $O(k \log_2 p)$ bits.

- For all n participants, the total communication is $O(nk \log_2 p)$ bits.

2) *Participant to Dealer Communication:* For each participant P_i :

- **Challenge Transmission:**

- In each of the k iterations, the participant sends a challenge bit $c \in \{0, 1\}$.

- The total communication per participant is k bits.

- **Total Participant to Dealer Communication:**

- For all n participants, the total communication is nk bits.

C. Optimization Considerations

1) Choice of Parameters:

- **Degree of Isogenies (ℓ):**

- Selecting small degrees for isogenies (ℓ) reduces the computational cost for both the dealer and participants.

- However, smaller ℓ may require more iterations (k) in the ZKP to achieve the desired security level.

- A balance must be struck between computational efficiency and security requirements.

- **Number of ZKP Iterations (k):**

- Increasing k reduces the soundness error exponentially ($\epsilon = 2^{-k}$).

- The value of k should be chosen to meet the desired security level while keeping computational and communication overhead manageable.

- Typical values of k range from 40 to 128 for practical security levels.

2) Parallelization:

- **Dealer's Computations:**

- The dealer's computations for isogeny generation and ZKP preparation for different participants are independent.

- These tasks can be parallelized across multiple processors or machines to reduce total computation time.

- **Participant's Computations:**

- Participants can parallelize the verification steps in the ZKP protocol, especially when k is large.

3) *Efficient Algorithms:*

• **Optimized Isogeny Computations:**

- Implementing efficient algorithms for isogeny computation can significantly reduce computational overhead.
- Techniques such as optimal strategies for evaluating Vélu's formulas [14] can be employed.

• **Field Arithmetic:**

- Efficient implementations of arithmetic operations in $\mathbb{F}_{p^2}$ are critical.
- Using Montgomery multiplication or other optimized algorithms can enhance performance.

D. Comparison with Existing Protocols

We compare the efficiency of our protocol with other VSS schemes, focusing on computational and communication complexities.

1) *Shamir's Secret Sharing Scheme:*

• **Computational Complexity:**

- Dealer's computation: $O(nt)$ for share computation.
- Participant's computation: $O(t^2)$ for secret reconstruction.

• **Communication Complexity:**

- Dealer to participant: Transmits s_i of size $\log_2 p$ bits.
- No additional communication for verifiability.

2) *Pedersen's VSS Scheme:*

• **Computational Complexity:**

- Dealer computes commitments using discrete logarithms, adding $O(nt)$ group operations.
- Participants verify commitments, requiring additional computations.

• **Communication Complexity:**

- Dealer sends commitments to participants, increasing communication overhead.

3) *Proposed Protocol:*

• **Computational Complexity:**

- Dealer's computation: $O(nt) + O(nk)$, where k is the number of ZKP iterations.
- Participant's computation: $O(k) + O(t^2)$.
- Additional overhead due to isogeny computations and ZKPs is acceptable for post-quantum security.

• **Communication Complexity:**

- Dealer to participant: $O(k \log_2 p)$ bits per participant.
- Participant to dealer: k bits per participant.
- Communication overhead is moderate and scalable.

4) *Summary of Comparisons:*

E. Practical Considerations

1) *Implementation Feasibility:*

- The proposed protocol is suitable for practical implementation in systems where post-quantum security is a priority.

- The computational overhead is manageable with modern computing resources, especially when parallelization is employed.
- Communication overhead is acceptable for applications with moderate network capabilities.

2) *Security vs. Efficiency Trade-offs:*

- The increased computational and communication costs compared to classical schemes are justified by the enhanced security provided against quantum adversaries.
- System designers must consider the security requirements of their application to determine the suitability of the protocol.

F. Conclusion of Efficiency Analysis

The efficiency analysis demonstrates that the proposed VSS protocol achieves a reasonable balance between security and performance. While there is additional overhead due to isogeny computations and Zero-Knowledge Proofs, these costs are justified by the protocol's robustness against quantum attacks. Optimization strategies, such as choosing appropriate parameters and employing efficient algorithms, can further enhance the protocol's practicality for real-world applications.

1) *Comparison with Existing Protocols:* Compared to classical VSS schemes like Shamir's Secret Sharing [8], which require $O(nt)$ computations for share generation and $O(t^2)$ for reconstruction, our protocol adds the overhead of isogeny computations and ZKP generation/verification.

However, these additional computations are necessary for post-quantum security and verifiability. With optimized implementations and parameter choices, the computational overhead can be kept within practical limits.

VI. COMPARISON WITH EXISTING PROTOCOLS

In this section, we compare our proposed protocol with existing VSS schemes in terms of security, computational efficiency, communication overhead, and post-quantum resistance.

A. Comparison with Shamir's Secret Sharing Scheme

1) *Security:* Shamir's Secret Sharing (SSS) [8] is secure under the assumption of the hardness of polynomial interpolation with insufficient points. However, it lacks verifiability and is vulnerable to quantum attacks due to Shor's algorithm [1].

2) *Computational Efficiency:* SSS has low computational overhead:

- Dealer's computation: $O(nt)$.
- Participant's computation: $O(t^2)$ for reconstruction.

3) *Communication Overhead:* Communication involves sending shares s_i of size $\log p$ bits. No additional overhead for verifiability.

4) *Post-Quantum Resistance:* SSS is not post-quantum secure due to vulnerabilities in the underlying arithmetic operations against quantum algorithms.

Protocol	Computational Complexity	Communication Complexity
Shamir's Scheme	Dealer: $O(nt)$ Participant: $O(t^2)$	Dealer to participant: $O(\log_2 p)$ bits
Pedersen's VSS	Dealer: $O(nt)$ Participant: Higher than Shamir's	Increased due to commitments
Proposed Protocol	Dealer: $O(nt + nk)$ Participant: $O(k + t^2)$	Dealer to participant: $O(k \log_2 p)$ bits Participant to dealer: k bits

TABLE I

COMPARISON OF COMPUTATIONAL AND COMMUNICATION COMPLEXITIES

B. Comparison with Pedersen's VSS Scheme

1) *Security*: Pedersen's VSS [10] adds verifiability using commitments based on discrete logarithms. Security relies on the hardness of the Discrete Logarithm Problem (DLP), which is broken by quantum algorithms.

2) *Computational Efficiency*: Additional computations for commitments:

- Dealer computes commitments for coefficients.
- Participants verify commitments.

3) *Communication Overhead*: Increased due to transmission of commitments.

4) *Post-Quantum Resistance*: Not secure against quantum attacks due to reliance on DLP.

C. Comparison with Post-Quantum VSS Schemes

1) *Code-Based VSS*: Code-based VSS schemes rely on error-correcting codes for security [11]. They are considered post-quantum secure.

2) *Lattice-Based VSS*: Lattice-based schemes use hard problems in lattice mathematics [12]. They offer post-quantum security but may have higher computational overhead.

D. Advantages of the Proposed Protocol

- **Post-Quantum Security**: Based on the hardness of the SIP, believed to be resistant to quantum attacks.
- **Verifiability**: Integrates ZKPs to ensure share validity.
- **Efficiency**: Computational costs are reasonable and can be optimized.

VII. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a Verifiable Secret Sharing protocol based on isogenies of supersingular elliptic curves, offering robust security in a post-quantum context. Detailed mathematical proofs demonstrate the protocol's correctness, security, and efficiency. The integration of Zero-Knowledge Proofs ensures verifiability without compromising the secret or the isogenies used. This protocol represents a significant contribution to the development of cryptographic systems secure against quantum adversaries.

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